

Supplementary File 1

Student Feedback Questionnaire: Pyramidal Problem-Based Learning Intervention

Purpose of the Questionnaire

This questionnaire was designed to evaluate postgraduate students' perceptions of a pyramidal problem-based learning (PBL) intervention incorporating structured mind mapping for teaching immunity to COVID-19. The questionnaire assessed perceived impact on conceptual understanding, engagement, communication skills, confidence in problem-based learning, and preparedness for independent study. Participation was voluntary, and responses were collected anonymously. Completion of the questionnaire implied consent to participate.

Instructions to Participants

Please indicate the extent to which you agree or disagree with each of the following statements based on your experience during the learning activity. There are no right or wrong answers. Your responses will be kept confidential and used solely for academic and research purposes.

Response Scale

Each statement was rated using a 4-point Likert scale:

- 1 – Strongly Disagree
- 2 – Disagree
- 3 – Agree
- 4 – Strongly Agree

Section A: Learning and Conceptual Understanding

1. The pyramidal problem-based learning activity helped me to better understand the immunological mechanisms involved in COVID-19 immunity.
2. The use of mind mapping helped me to organise complex immunological concepts in a clear and meaningful way.
3. The activity improved my ability to integrate innate and adaptive immune responses related to viral infections.

Section B: Engagement and Learning Experience

4. The learning activity was more engaging than a traditional lecture on the same topic.
5. The group-based structure encouraged active participation and discussion.
6. The activity maintained my interest and attention throughout the session.

Section C: Communication and Collaborative Skills

7. The small-group discussions improved my ability to explain immunological concepts to peers.
8. The whole-class synthesis phase improved my confidence in presenting scientific ideas.
9. The activity enhanced my teamwork and collaborative learning skills.

Section D: Confidence and Preparedness for Independent Learning

10. The activity increased my confidence in participating in problem-based learning activities.
11. I feel better prepared to engage in guided independent study or research-oriented learning following this activity.
12. The learning approach supported my transition from lecture-based learning to independent problem solving.

Section E: Overall Perception

13. Overall, this pyramidal problem-based learning approach was effective for learning complex immunological topics.
14. I would recommend the use of this learning approach for other topics in immunology.
15. I would like to see similar problem-based learning activities incorporated into future modules.

Optional Open-Ended Question

16. Please provide any additional comments or suggestions regarding the pyramidal problem-based learning activity.

Supplementary Table 1: Mapping of Questionnaire Sections and Items to Predefined Analytical Domains

Domain	Questionnaire Section	Matching Items
Enhanced conceptual understanding	Section A	Q1, Q2, Q3
Increased engagement during learning	Section B	Q4, Q5, Q6
Improved communication skills	Section C	Q7, Q8, Q9
Increased confidence in PBL	Section D	Q10
Preparedness for independent study	Section D	Q11, Q12

Note. This table presents the alignment of questionnaire sections and individual items with the predefined analytical domains used to evaluate the pyramidal problem-based learning (PBL) intervention. Each domain represents a key outcome of interest, and the corresponding

questionnaire items indicate which aspects of student perception were assessed within each domain.